

E-Content Development

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Abstract:

The MHRD, under its National Mission on Education through ICT (NME-ICT), has allocated funds to the Consortium of Educational Communication (CEC) for the development of e-content for 87 undergraduate (UG) subjects. The content and its quality are key components of a robust teaching-learning system. It is proposed to create high-quality, curriculum-based, interactive content across all disciplines of the social sciences, arts, fine arts & humanities, natural & mathematical sciences, and linguistics & languages. E-Content, so developed, would be available on open access through a dedicated Learning Management System. Development of e-content is a specialized job requiring skills of a video producer, web designer, and instructional designer. However, a faculty or a scientist involved in teaching and research is perfectly suitable and capable of preparing basic materials that can be transformed into e-content with the intervention of a web designer and professionals with ICT skills. This document is designed to guide the content writer to write an e-content module for a given paper, along with a description of multimedia contents and instructions to the graphical designer/ animator

Keywords: *E-Content, Analyses, Development, Testing, etc.*

Introduction:

The purpose of e-content development is to create an information rich society. Every one in the society is empowered to create, receive, share and utilize information for their progress. Very well designed, developed and validated e-content will provide access to high quality meaningful digital content and serve as an effective virtual teacher. E-content design, development and approach will depend upon the nature of the content and the learners. It will also depend on the quality and complexity the learning you wish to create. Various instructional design models are available according to our requirements. Most of the models involve the process of analyzing the learner needs and goals of the instructional material development, development of a delivery system and content, pilot study of the material developed,

implementation, evaluating, refining the materials etc.

In designing and development of E-content we have to adopt one of the instructional design models based on our requirements.

Objective:

1. To study the e-content development
2. To Study of the Guidelines for Developing eContent
3. To study the content in e-development.

Methodology:

here are we use secondary data collection method in research work. All collected by books, magazines, Internet etc.

Phases of e-content development o In e-content development aspects consists of six phases:

Analysis → Design → Development → Testing → Implementation and → Evaluation

1] The Analysis Phase: It is the most important as it identifies areas in our current situation. This phase accountability considered by the views of subject experts, target audiences, objectives and its goals. In this phase, we must know the audience, and their skill, budget of the econtent, delivery methods and its constraints with due dates

2] The Design Phase: It involves the complete design of the learning solution. It helps to plan of an e-content preparation. In this phase, we must know the planning, use of relevant software; required skills; creative and innovative interactions of subject contents like texts, pictures, videos and suitable animations.

3] The Development Phase: It concerns the actual production of the e-content design. It helps to create the e-content by mixing of texts, audio, video, animations, references, blogs, links, and MCQs (multiple choice questions) with some programming specifications like home, exit, next etc.

4] The Testing phase: It helps to administer the e-content in the actual educational field. In this phase, we must test the spelling mistakes, content errors, clarity of pictures, relevant videos, appropriate audios, timing of animations, and hyperlinks

5] The Implementation Phase: It helps to administer the e-content to the target audience. This phase explains how to install and how to use

it and their difficulties experienced while using e-content. It checks the product accuracy and quality maintenance.

6] The Evaluation Phase: It helps to satisfy the e-content and its effectiveness. This phase considers feedback from both learners and instructors. After the feedback reactions, the e-content is designed again as postproduction for effective delivery of e-content

Conclusion:

We analyses to How Develop e-content in modern education.

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